

“I Will Become What I Choose to Become”

Exodus 3:14, 15

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

Exodus 3:14, 15

וַיֹּאמֶר אֱלֹהִים אֶל־מֹשֶׁה אֲהִיָּה אֲשֶׁר אֲהִיָּה וַיֹּאמֶר כֹּה תֹאמַר לִבְנֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל אֲהִיָּה שְׁלַחֲנִי אֵלֵיכֶם
וַיֹּאמֶר עוֹד אֱלֹהִים אֶל־מֹשֶׁה כֹּה־תֹאמַר אֶל־בְּנֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי אֲבוֹתֵיכֶם אֱלֹהֵי אַבְרָהָם אֱלֹהֵי יִצְחָק וְאֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב שְׁלַחֲנִי
אֵלֵיכֶם וְהִשְׁמִי לְעֵלְמָּה זֶה זְכָרִי לְדֹר דָּר

After Jehovah* had told Moses, “let me send you to Pharaoh, and you bring my people the sons of Israel out of Egypt”(verse 10), Moses said: “Who am I that I should go to Pharaoh and that I have to bring the sons of Israel out of Egypt?” (verse 11). To this Jehovah began to reassure Moses that he would be capable of this assignment. He began with this encouragement in verse 12:

Because I shall prove to be with you, and this is the sign for you that it is I who have sent you: After you have brought the people out of Egypt, YOU people will serve the [true] God on this mountain.

“Because I shall prove to be with you” translates כִּי־אֲהִיָּה עִמָּךְ. Other translations are: “Certainly I will be with thee” (KJV, ASV), “I will be with you” (NIV, NLT, CEV, GNT). In explaining the significance of the verb אֲהִיָּה, Hastings (vol. II, p. 199) put it this way:

With regard to this verb, first, it does not mean ‘to be’ essentially or ontologically, but phenomenally; and secondly, the impf. has not the sense of a present (‘am’) but of a fut. (‘will be’). In Ex 3^{off}, when Moses demurred to go to Egypt, God assured him, saying, כִּי־אֲהִיָּה עִמָּךְ.

* See Appendix, page 5.

Even though he was standing in front of the “sign” of God’s presence—the burning bush—Moses was not yet comfortable with God’s request.

Suppose I am now come to the sons of Israel and I do say to them, ‘The God of YOUR forefathers has sent me to YOU,’ and they do say to me, ‘What is his name?’ What shall I say to them?’ 14 At this God said to Moses: “I SHALL PROVE TO BE WHAT I SHALL PROVE TO BE [אֶהְיֶה אֲשֶׁר אֶהְיֶה].” And he added: “This is what you are to say to the sons of Israel, ‘I SHALL PROVE TO BE [אֶהְיֶה] has sent me to YOU.’”

God’s first statement in verse 14 is in response to “What is his name?”; the second is in response to “What shall I say to them?”

S.R. Driver translated the two imperfects אֶהְיֶה אֲשֶׁר אֶהְיֶה “I will be that I will be” adding “The words are evidently intended as an interpretation of the name... The explanation is thus of a character to reassure Moses” (*Exodus*). GKC (§75 *hh*) translated the verb אֶהְיֶה as “I will be”, citing Jeremiah 31:1: “At that time,” is the utterance of Jehovah, “I shall become [אֶהְיֶה] God to all the families of Israel”. Fox translated the phrase, “I will be-there howsoever I will be-there”, Rotherham, “I Will Become whatsoever I please” and the 2013 NW, “I Will Become What I Choose to Become”.

Before the sons of Israel were released from Egypt Jehovah wanted them to know something about him. Israel was about to form a closer relationship with Jehovah that would be tested throughout the Exodus. Jehovah told them, ‘I will become what ever you need’. In other words, whatever Moses and the nation of Israel needed as they extricated themselves from Egypt, Jehovah would supply it, that would be Jehovah’s reputation, his name. *Draw Close* (p. 10) explained it this way:

No matter what obstacle loomed before them, no matter how difficult the predicament in which they might find themselves, Jehovah would become whatever was needed in order to deliver them from slavery and bring them into the Promised Land.

The Watchtower (2010:7:1:4) added:

In order to accomplish his loving purpose for mankind, he can become whatever he pleases, filling whatever role is needed. Knowing Jehovah by name thus involves understanding and appreciating his many roles.

As with all reputations/names, they are a cluster of qualities, attitudes, roles, abilities, actions over time.

Let's now look at the progression of God's statements and how the two pauses are used.

Verse 12:

כִּי־אֶהְיֶה עִמָּךְ

Because I shall prove to be with you

Verse 14:

אֶהְיֶה אֲשֶׁר אֶהְיֶה

I shall prove to be what I shall prove to be [pause]

אֶהְיֶה שְׁלַחְנִי אֵלֵיכֶם

This is what you are to say to the sons of Israel, 'I shall prove to be has sent me to you [pause]

Verse 15:

יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי אֲבוֹתֵיכֶם

אֱלֹהֵי אַבְרָהָם אֱלֹהֵי יִצְחָק וְאֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב שְׁלַחְנִי אֵלֵיכֶם

זֶה־שְׁמִי לְעֹלָם

וְזֶה זְכָרִי לְדֹר דֹּר

*Jehovah the God of YOUR forefathers,
the God of Abraham, the God of Isaac and the God of Jacob, has sent me to YOU.
This is my name to time indefinite,
and this is the memorial of me to generation after generation.*

Four times God uses the word אֶהְיֶה as he endeavoured to put Moses at ease. He introduced this term in the phrase כִּי־אֶהְיֶה עִמָּךְ. As noted, this term is used for his reputation.

The first use of אֶהְיֶה prepared the way for Moses to understand the bigger statement: אֶהְיֶה אֲשֶׁר אֶהְיֶה. Then God paused to allow Moses time to think about the implications of this promise. It is good for us to meditate on these implications.

After the pause, God said that Moses was the representative of אֶהְיֶה.

Then God paused again.

Then came the climax in four cola. Now God exchanges אֶהְיֶה with יְהוָה, his name. אֶהְיֶה שְׁלַחְנִי אֵלֵיכֶם, "I shall prove to be has sent me to you", is expanded into יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי

אֲבֹתֵיכֶם אֱלֹהֵי אַבְרָהָם אֱלֹהֵי יִצְחָק וְאֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב שְׁלַחְנִי אֵלֵיכֶם, “*Jehovah* the God of YOUR forefathers, the God of Abraham, the God of Isaac and the God of Jacob, *has sent me to you*”. Israel should remember how Jehovah had been whatever the patriarchs needed—salvation, protection, prosperity, mercy, hope, direction.

Moreover, as the third colon states, this is Jehovah’s reputation—his name—forever.

And in the final colon God told Moses that this name should never be forgotten.

So this declaration reaches to our day and beyond. His name has not changed.

Perhaps after this God hoped that he had said enough for Moses to happily accept the assignment.

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵי does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ASV *The Holy Bible* known as *Revised Version, Standard American Edition*, Watchtower Bible and Tract Society, 1901.
- CEV *Holy Bible, Contemporary English Version*, British and Foreign Bible Society, 1996.
- Draw Close* *Draw Close to Jehovah*, Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, Inc. International Bible Students Association, Brooklyn, New York, 2002.
- Driver, *Exodus* S.R. Driver, *The Book of Exodus, the Cambridge Bible for Schools and Colleges*, Cambridge University Press, 1953.
- Fox Everett Fox, *The Five Books of Moses, A New Translation with Introductions, Commentary, and Notes*, The Harvill Press, 1995.
- GKC Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar, Wilhelm Gesenius, edited and enlarged by Emil Kautzsch, translated into English by Arthur Ernest Cowley, Oxford, 1910.
- GNT *Good News Bible*, British and Foreign Bible Society, 1994.
- KJV *King James Version*.
- Hastings *A Dictionary of the Bible, Dealing with its Language, Literature, and Contents Including the Biblical Theology*, edited by James Hastings, John A. Selbie, H.B. Swete, T&T Clarke, Edinburgh, 1900.
- Insight*. *Insight on the Scriptures*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania, 2018.
- M Masoretic text found in Codex Leningrad B 19A.
- mwb* *Our Christian Life and Ministry—Meeting Workbook*, Christian Congregation of Jehovah's Witnesses.
- NIV *The Holy Bible, New International Version*, Hodder and Stoughton, 1980.
- NLT *New Living Translation*, Tyndale House Foundation, 2015.
- NW 2013 *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures (Study*

Edition), Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania, 2013.

Rotherham *The Emphasised Bible*, Joseph Bryant Rotherham, The Standard Publishing Company, Cincinnati, 1897.

The Watchtower *The Watchtower*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania.

Vow. J.P. Fokkelman, *Narrative Art and Poetry in the Books of Samuel, King David*, Volume IV, Van Gorcum, 1993.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984 [NW], unless otherwise indicated.